

*Development and Application of the 188-220 Protocol Test Tool Network Analyzer
(PTTNA) Prototype*

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Abstract

The 188-220 Protocol Test Tool (PTT) Suite was developed by the US Army CECOM Software Engineering Center. It combines software and hardware to monitor, decode, display, and analyze MIL-STD-188-220 traffic on the Combat Net Radio (CNR) network. It operates under the Microsoft Windows NT operating system on a Pentium-class personal computer.

This paper briefly describes the entire suite of tools, but focuses on the development process, functionality, and application of the Network Analyzer, the suite's most recent addition. This tool was utilized extensively throughout the Force Battle Command Brigade and Below (FBCB2) Setup and Connectivity Testing and the FBCB2 Limited User Test (LUT) during the summer of 1998 to test and troubleshoot CNR networks.

Introduction

The Army has embarked upon a program for digitizing the battlefield to meet the challenges of the 21st century. In order to support the required integration and mobility, the MIL-STD-188-220 protocol was developed.

MIL-STD-188-220B, the current version of the protocol, is a communications protocol for exchanging digital data over Combat Net Radio (CNR) networks. This protocol is a key component of the Tactical Internet. The first implementations of MIL-STD-188-220A, the previous version of the protocol,

were exercised during Task Force XXI (TFXXI).

Since this is a military protocol, no commercial tools were available to test and debug MIL-STD-188-220 implementations. As a result, CECOM took the initiative to develop a set of tools that would aid in their testing and troubleshooting.

The first section of this paper describes the components that comprise the 188-220 Protocol Test Tool (PTT) suite. The remainder of the paper focuses on the PTT Network Analyzer, including how it evolved, its functionality, and its application.

188-220 PTT Suite

The 188-220 PTT suite is comprised of the following components:

- The *Monitor/Decoder*, which allows users to passively tap into the communications line and record, decode, and display all MIL-STD-188-220B traffic in real-time
- The *Conformance Tester*, which allows one-on-one testing of MIL-STD-188-220B implementations by providing a stimuli of scripted traffic and evaluating the implementation's response against the expected response
- The *Network Analyzer*, which transforms the messages collected by the *Monitor/Decoder* into network-oriented information, such as connectivity data

and statistics on radios and hosts that are network members.

The *Monitor/Decoder* was very useful during TFXXI system certification testing. The CECOM Digital Integrated Laboratory (DIL) was responsible for certification testing of all systems participating in TFXXI to ensure interoperability. In order to make this determination for systems communicating over CNR, the DIL used the *Monitor/Decoder*. This tool has also been utilized by MIL-STD-188-220B developers in order to test and troubleshoot implementations during the development process.

Developers have used the *Conformance Tester* as a traffic stimulator and to evaluate their implementations against MIL-STD-188-220B. This tool will also be utilized during certification testing of systems participating in First Digitized Division (FDD) scheduled for October 2000. The *Conformance Tester* is currently being enhanced to improve on the current capabilities and add functionality.

Both the *Monitor/Decoder* and the *Conformance Tester* are most useful in laboratory environments, where analysts knowledgeable in the protocol have the time to analyze the traffic and make determinations based on traffic patterns or a system's actual response to stimuli. The *Network Analyzer*, on the other hand, can be used in a laboratory or a field environment. The insight into CNR networks provided by this tool is invaluable, and the tool is simple enough to use in a high-stress field environment. The remainder of the paper is dedicated to discussion of the *Network Analyzer*.

Network Analyzer Development Approach

The *Network Analyzer* was viewed as the tool with the most potential in terms of number of users due to its flexibility, functionality, and ease of use. In order to

ensure an effective end-product, however, CECOM SEC sought out potential users who were experienced with CNR networks and would therefore be able to provide insight into key requirements for such a tool. These users included developers of MIL-STD-188-220B implementations as well as soldiers from the 4th Infantry Division (4ID) in Ft. Hood, TX. These soldiers had participated in TFXXI and had found the lack of available troubleshooting tools for CNR networks troubling; this lack of tools complicated the exercise due to the lack of insight into CNR network problems and, therefore, solutions.

The users were very forthcoming with requirements, and these requirements form the basis of the current *Network Analyzer*. An overview of the tool's functionality and specific features is provided in the next section.

Once concrete requirements were obtained from potential users and documented, design of the *Network Analyzer* began. Object-oriented techniques were followed, permitting clear distinctions within the code among objects, data, and methods. This facilitated coding the *Network Analyzer* as well as modifying and adding functionality later on.

The *Network Analyzer* operates on data collected by the *Monitor/Decoder*; thus, both tools must be running in real-time in order to obtain network views and information. The *Monitor/Decoder*, designed with this function in mind, stores all collected messages in a database that is accessible by the *Network Analyzer* in real-time.

Testing of the *Network Analyzer* was performed both in-house and on-site at the Electronic Proving Ground (EPG), Ft. Huachuca, AZ. In-house testing allowed for initial functionality bugs to be located and fixed, but a sufficiently large network of radios, as well as multiple networks, were not available to test the tool as it would be

utilized in the field. Therefore, CECOM SEC traveled several times to EPG, coordinating *Network Analyzer* testing with Internet Controller (INC) and FBCB2 pre-LUT testing. Thus, when the tool was delivered to Ft. Hood in June 1998, CECOM SEC had tested it sufficiently to establish confidence in its ability to function properly and reliably.

Network Analyzer Functionality and Features

The *Network Analyzer* permits users real-time visibility and insight into CNR networks. It allows users to view the connectivity of radios and hosts on any network within range of the radio that the tools are connected to. It also provides statistics on radio, host, and network performance.

Connection to the Network. Figure 1 displays how the *Monitor/Decoder* and the *Network Analyzer* connect to the network.

Figure 1. Connection to the Network

As depicted in the figure, a computer running the *Monitor/Decoder* and *Network Analyzer* software is connected either between an INC and a radio, or directly to a radio. The computer must be equipped with a 188-220 communications board, available through CECOM. This connection permits complete visibility into the entire CNR network. Alternatively, users may connect to a monitoring radio (not part of any network) which can be used to "surf" all networks within its range. This is convenient if there are many networks to monitor, as it allows monitoring of all

networks within range to be performed from a single location.

Network Analyzer Features. Upon user-selection of a network, the skeleton configuration appears as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Skeleton Network Configuration

Blue circles depict radios that are network members; attached FBCB2 hosts appear as white labels adjacent to the radios. This configuration indicates only who should be on the network; radios and hosts have not yet transmitted traffic, but those visible are network members.

As radios and/or hosts start transmitting messages, they turn green. If radios who are not network members (that is, they were not displayed in blue in the initial configuration), are detected transmitting on the network, they are displayed in yellow. Figure 3 depicts this scenario.

Figure 3. Radios and Hosts Transmitting

Users may also select a time interval after which, if radios and/or hosts have not transmitted, they turn red. This is also demonstrated in Figure 3.

Connectivity lines that detail radios talking to one another as well as the type of communication (i.e., transmit only, transmit/receive, or receive only) can also be displayed. Additionally, charts for each radio and host display the volume and origin/destination of traffic (see Figure 4). The combination of these two features provide users with invaluable insight into the network traffic patterns.

Figure 4. Radio Traffic Chart

The *Network Analyzer* also provides real-time statistics on the entire network, including throughput in bits/second, volume of various types of messages traversing the network, and the volume of bad vs. good messages on the network. Figure 5 shows an image of the Network Statistics window.

Figure 5. Network Statistics

Network Analyzer Application

The *Network Analyzer* was initially utilized during the summer of 1998 by TRW, the FBCB2 developers, at FBCB2 Setup and Connectivity Testing in Ft. Hood, Texas. At the start of testing, they utilized a single computer running the tool and configured it so that they could monitor all nets within range of the radio it was connected to from that one location. This is demonstrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Network Analyzer Configuration at Ft. Hood

As seen in Figure 6, the computer running the tool was connected to a monitoring SINCGARS radio located in TRW's field trailer. By changing the frequency on the radio and the tool in tandem, TRW had instant visibility into any network within range of the monitoring radio. Figure 6 shows the radio (and the tool) tuned to the 990 frequency, which provides instant visibility into this network. If users wanted to view a different network, they needed only to change the frequency on the radio and the tool; as long as that network was within range of the monitoring radio, users were provided with instant real-time visibility into this network.

TRW used the *Network Analyzer* throughout FBCB2 Setup and Connectivity Testing as well as during the FBCB2 LUT, which took place in August 1998. TRW found the tool extremely useful because it provided them with instant real-time visibility into the CNR

networks, which they had never had previously. This allowed for rapid troubleshooting since many problems were surfaced almost immediately. Often problems were simple to solve; for example, radios that were displayed as blue (i.e., never came up) would sometimes be turned off, or configured improperly, or not connected to an antenna. These are easy problems to fix, but would have been very difficult to identify without the insight provided by the tool.

A more complicated problem isolated by the *Network Analyzer* was related to the INC MIB. Users were troubleshooting a network using the tool and noticed that the host names of the network servers did not match the hosts that were transmitting. After some investigation, they discovered that two new servers had been added to the network but the MIB had not been correctly updated, causing these two servers to have duplicate radio addresses with the original two servers. This was causing confusion on the network, as every radio must have a unique address. Once the problem was discovered, the MIB was immediately updated and downloaded to all of the INCs participating in the test.

The tool provided users with unprecedented visibility and insight into CNR networks, thereby allowing rapid problem isolation and troubleshooting. Due to this, the tool received rave reviews from users; never before had they had access to a tool that provided them with that level of real-time visibility and insight into CNR networks.

The *Network Analyzer* subsequently received a great deal of visibility within the network management community. Program managers and users attended several briefings and demonstrations of the tool and were impressed with its capabilities.

Future Plans

Since both users and program managers were impressed with the *Network Analyzer*,

discussions ensued in terms of what could be done to enhance and modify it to create an optimal CNR network management tool for the soldier in the field. A proposal was developed by CECOM SEC and submitted to the appropriate Program Manager. Unfortunately, there was no immediate funding available to proceed with the modifications and enhancements requested by users and documented in the proposal. However, funding is currently being sought for this project in order to enable CECOM SEC to work with program managers and users to provide soldiers with this valuable tool.

Due to the lack of funds, no further work is being done to enhance or modify the *Network Analyzer* at this time. Users can continue to utilize the tool as is during upcoming exercises and tests. If and when funding becomes available, CECOM SEC stands ready to perform the modifications and enhancements in the proposal and provide a valuable tool to the soldier in the field.